

Arab Republic of Egypt
Institute of Arab Research and Studies
Department of Educational Research and Studies

**Psychological resilience as a mediating
variable between traumatic events and
Psychological pain among A sample of
workers in the Medical sector.**

A thesis Submitted by
Gergess Makram Labeeb

*For Fulfillment of Master Degree in "Mental Health
Specialization".*

Supervised by
Prof. Dr. Iman Fawzy Shaheen
Professor of Mental Health and Psychological Counseling,
Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University

2024

Summary

Introduction

Since the beginning of creation on Earth, humans have been and continue to be exposed to traumatic events throughout different stages of their lives. These events vary in intensity, the frequency with which an individual experiences the traumatic event, and its duration. The severity of the impact of traumatic events also differs based on the individual's perception, the effects of the resulting symptoms, and the amount of psychological pain they experience. Each individual may encounter traumatic events at least once in their lives, which exposes them to social and psychological suffering (psychological pain) in response to feelings of insecurity, lack of appreciation, or feelings of being unloved and unvalued, or as a result of material and moral losses. These painful emotions operate in two ways: first, they carry knowledge about the traumatic event, and second, they present the pain itself. The variation in the severity of these traumatic events, adversities, and their consequences depends on the cognitive functions of each individual and how they cope with them.

In the face of trauma, People find themselves either yielding to the feelings of pain, fleeing from them, allowing time to pass in hopes it will heal their wounds, or overcoming them through a protective mechanism known as psychological resilience. This resilience refers to the ability to adapt when facing traumatic events, and it relies on several factors. These factors help the individual return to their pre-trauma state.

Psychological pain symptoms are often secondary to more primary emotions such as feelings of loneliness, loss, shame, guilt, and injustice, which are the primary emotions resulting from traumatic events.

Therefore, it is important to understand both ourselves and others, as well as our pain and theirs, and to recognize the factors that reduce this psychological pain (resilience in the current research). This is because there may come a point when the emotions resulting from the trauma are so painful that they become unbearable, at which point the function of finding meaning ceases, and it becomes a threat to psychological existence.

Problem of the Study

The Egyptians have encountered numerous traumatic events that result in psychological pain, which may be bearable for one individual but overwhelming for another. For some, it completely dominates their life, making them feel that life has lost its meaning, leading to a sense of worthlessness, rejection, and imbalance in relationships with others. It causes a loss of the deeper meaning of life and a lack of purpose. Moreover, traumatic events have shaped a distinctive personality pattern in the minds and hearts of Egyptians, setting them apart from other nations, and in turn, influencing their resilience. Previous studies have shown a correlation between the genetic factors of populations and their resilience. (Kosuke, Michael, & Cecilia, 2019, pp. 61- 71).

Previous studies have shown a strong correlation between traumatic events and psychological resilience, with varying degrees across different populations, such as the study by (Zheng, 2015). Since exposure to traumatic events causes psychological, emotional, or social pain depending on the type and source of the trauma, and since psychological resilience is the factor that helps individuals overcome such events—this has been proven in studies examining the two variables of the current study, traumatic events and psychological pain, such as the

study by Gregory Bartoszek et al. in 2017. There have also been studies that examined the relationship between traumatic events and psychological resilience, including the study by Bolsinger et al. in 2018. Additionally, there have been studies that examined the mediating role of resilience, such as the study by Onat Yetim in Turkey in 2022.

From here, the researcher sees the problem of the study as testing the relationship between the variables and examining whether psychological resilience plays a mediating role between traumatic events and the degree of psychological pain. Based on the previous context, the study seeks to answer the following main research question:

“ What is the nature of the relationship between psychological pain and psychological resilience among individuals who have experienced traumatic events?”.

Objectives of the Study

Given the assumed relationship between the study variables, the study aims to:

Identify the nature of the relationship between psychological pain and psychological resilience among individuals who have experienced traumatic events.

Explore differences in levels of psychological resilience among the sample based on the following demographic variables: gender, education level, profession, and marital status.

Explore differences in traumatic events among the sample based on the following demographic variables: gender, education level, profession, and marital status.

Explore differences in levels of psychological pain among the sample based on the following demographic variables: gender, education level, profession, and marital status.

Importance of the Study

The importance of the study lies in the nature of its variables, which include psychological pain, psychological resilience, and traumatic events. This study also contributes to addressing the existing gap in local studies, according to the researcher's knowledge, regarding psychological pain. Based on this, the researcher has aimed to achieve the following objectives:

First: Theoretical Importance

Contributing to the Arab community with this study, given its scarcity in the Arabic language, particularly regarding psychological pain, based on the researcher's efforts.

Identifying the most common traumatic events in Egyptian society through the questionnaire used in the study, which may help researchers take necessary measures in future studies.

Drawing attention to a group that suffers from pain that is difficult to express, unlike those who experience physical pain.

Second: Practical Importance

Providing Arabic-language scales for traumatic events and psychological pain, which are lacking in Arabic research literature, based on the researcher's knowledge after reviewing numerous foreign scales.

Offering this study to professionals in the fields of counseling, psychological guidance, and mental health, with the hope that it

will alleviate the suffering of those experiencing psychological pain.

Contributing to specialists in the field of psychological counseling by working to reduce the impact of psychological pain through the development of psychological resilience, according to the expected hypotheses.

Identifying the characteristics of psychologically resilient personalities and utilizing them in the counseling process, as well as developing guidance programs aimed at enhancing psychological resilience to be more effective in reducing the psychological pain resulting from traumatic events.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1- "There is a fit for the proposed model of the relationship between traumatic events (as the independent variable), psychological resilience (as the mediating variable), and psychological pain (as the dependent variable) among a sample of medical sector employees." This hypothesis branches into the following sub-hypotheses:
 - A. "There is a direct effect of traumatic events on psychological resilience".
 - B. "There is a direct effect of psychological resilience on psychological pain".
 - C. "There is a direct effect of traumatic events on psychological pain".
 - D. "There is an indirect effect of traumatic events on psychological pain through psychological resilience".

- 2- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological resilience scale based on gender (Male – Female)".
- 3- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the traumatic events scale based on gender (Male – Female.)".
- 4- "There are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological pain scale based on gender (Male - Female".
- 5- "There are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological resilience scale based on profession".
- 6- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the traumatic events scale based on profession".
- 7- "There are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological pain scale based on profession".
- 8- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological resilience scale based on educational level (Higher Education - Postgraduate Studies)".
- 9- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the traumatic events scale based on educational level (Higher Education - Postgraduate Studies)".
- 10- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological pain scale based on educational level (Higher Education - Postgraduate Studies)".
- 11- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological resilience scale based on marital status (Single – Married)."

- 12- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the traumatic events scale based on marital status (Single - Married").
- 13- "There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the psychological pain scale based on marital status (Single – Married).”

Determinants of the Study

In this research, the researcher adhered to the following objective, spatial, temporal, and human limitations:

- A. **Objective Determinant:** These are the variables addressed in the study, which include traumatic events, psychological pain, and psychological resilience.
- B. **Human Determinant:** The sample consists of 159 individuals working in the medical sector in Egypt, including 99 males and 60 females.
- C. **Spatial Determinant:** The geographical scope is Greater Cairo, within the Arab Republic of Egypt.
- D. **Time limits:** The study was conducted in the year 2024.
- E. **Tools:**
- 1 - The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC 25), developed by Connor and Davidson (2003), which was translated and modified by the researcher.
 - 2 - A questionnaire on traumatic events, prepared by the researcher.
 - 3 - A psychological pain scale, prepared by the researcher.

Statistical Methods and Measures Used

- 1 - Pearson Correlation Coefficient.
- 2 - Confirmatory Factor Analysis.
- 3 - Cronbach's Alpha for reliability calculation.
- 4 - Spearman-Brown Coefficient for reliability calculation using the split-half method.
- 5 - Independent Samples t-test.
- 6 - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).
- 7 - One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Study Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive methodology, as it is suitable for the nature of the study.

Study results

1- Results of the first hypothesis:

There is a fit to the proposed model of the relationship between traumatic events (as an independent variable), psychological resilience (a mediating variable), and psychological pain (a dependent variable) in a sample of health workers.

The following sub-results branch out from it:

- A- There is a negative and statistically significant effect at the 0.01 level between traumatic events and psychological resilience, as the regression weight reached Standard -0.64 which is significant at the 0.01 level

- B- There is a direct negative and statistically significant effect at the 0.01 level between psychological RESILIENCE and psychological pain, as the regression weight reached Standard-0.46 which is significant at the 0.01 level
 - C- There is a direct, positive and statistically significant effect at the 0.01 level between traumatic events and psychological pain, as the regression weight reached Standard 0.26 which is significant at the 0.01 level
 - D - There is a positive and statistically significant indirect effect at the 0.01 level between traumatic events and psychological pain, as the regression weight reached Standard 0.29 which is significant at the 0.01 level
- 2- There are no statistically significant differences between males and females in all dimensions of the psychological resilience scale, as all “t” values were not statistically significant. It states: That "no “There are significant differences.
 - 3- There are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the traumatic events scale based on gender (Male – Female) , as the “t” value was not statistically significant.
 - 4- There are statistically significant differences between males and females in all dimensions of the psychological pain scale, as all of them were Values of the function "tat the 0.01 level in favor of females
 - 5- There are no statistically significant differences between the different professions in all dimensions and the total score of the psychological RESILIENCE, as all “F” values were not statistically significant.

- 6- There are no statistically significant differences between different professions in traumatic events, as the “F” value was not statistically significant.
- 7- There are no statistically significant differences between the different professions in all dimensions and the total score of the psychological pain scale, as all “F” values were statistically significant at the 0.01 level.
- 8- There are no statistically significant differences between those with higher qualifications and postgraduate studies in all dimensions of the psychological RESILIENCE scale, as all “t” values were not statistically significant.
- 9- There are no statistically significant differences between those with higher qualifications and postgraduate studies in traumatic events, as the “t” value was not statistically significant.
- 10- There are no statistically significant differences between those with higher qualifications and postgraduate studies in all dimensions of the psychological pain scale, as all “t” values were not statistically significant.
- 11- There are no statistically significant differences between unmarried and married people in all dimensions of the psychological resilience scale, as all of them were-values Not statistically significant.
- 12- There are no statistically significant differences between unmarried and married people in traumatic events, as the “t” value was not statistically significant.
- 13- There are no statistically significant differences between unmarried and married people in all dimensions of the psychological pain scale, as all of them were T values are not statistically significant.